

2025 DASH / IHDEA Joint Meeting Report

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- 3: Laboratory for Atmospheric and Space Physics
- 4: Met Office, Devon, UK
- 5: University of California, Los Angeles
- 6: NASA Goddard Space Flight Center
- 7: ESA European Space Astronomy Center
- 8: General Dynamics Mission Systems
- 9: George Mason University

A group photo of 2025 DASH/IHDEA attendees.

Executive Summary

The 2025 Data, Analysis, and Software in Heliophysics (DASH) and International Heliophysics Data Environment Alliance (IHDEA) Joint Meeting, held October 19–24 in San Antonio, Texas, was a successful iteration of this annual gathering to date, drawing strong attendance of 120 participants during DASH and 80 during IHDEA. The meeting brought together software developers, data engineers, and scientists from across the heliophysics community — spanning multiple international government agencies, non-governmental research organizations, and numerous universities — to focus on software, data standards, and analytical tools. New additions this year included a pre-conference proposal writing workshop, a dedicated poster session with lightning talks, and "Birds of a Feather" (BOF) sessions, all of which received strongly positive feedback. The hybrid format was well-executed, with high-quality audio and active management of virtual participation praised throughout.

DASH sessions covered a broad range of topics, from open-source collaboration in science data systems and ML/LLM (Machine Learning/Large Language Models) applications in heliophysics, to software for mission planning, heliophysics modeling infrastructure, and community building for Research Software Engineers (RSEs). During the IHDEA portion of the meeting, space agency reports, working group updates, and governance reforms dominated the agenda, including the approval of three bylaw changes to make the organization more agile and representative. A notable highlight was a focused session on Space Weather Standards and progress on SPASE 3.0, the next-generation metadata model for the international heliophysics data environment.

Looking ahead, the community identified several priorities: greater engagement with early-career researchers and underrepresented groups (such as modeling, RSEs, and ground-based observation communities), structured networking and career development opportunities, and a reduced and standardized set of meeting technologies. The 2026 DASH/IHDEA meeting will continue a growing record of a strong RSE community in Heliophysics in Dublin, Ireland, with organizers committed to incorporating this year's feedback to further strengthen the value and reach of these meetings.

Introduction: Meeting Purpose

The Data, Analysis, and Software in Heliophysics (DASH)) and the International Heliophysics Data Environment Alliance (IHDEA) joint meeting aims to bring together working practitioners of heliophysics data including scientists, software developers and engineers. Now in its third year, it remains the only meeting of its kind that focuses on the needs of Heliophysics software development supporting data, services, and scientific analysis capabilities (DASH) and the development and governance of standards in Heliophysics (IHDEA). Uniquely, the presentations and discussions featured at the DASH and IHDEA meetings regard the science accomplished as secondary to the software and standards' characteristics and capabilities.

Event Planning

This year's DASH/IHDEA meeting was held in San Antonio with onsite logistics led by Southwest Research Institute (SwRI). Due to complications in hosting the workshop on SwRI's campus, the decision was made to host the event in lively downtown San Antonio. This also provided workshop participants easy access to the vibrant culture of San Antonio and the large selection of restaurants near the Riverwalk.

Participation on the organizing committee was strictly voluntary and met consistently on a weekly basis starting around the January/February timeframe via Teams. The organizing committee was responsible for setting the overall "feel" of the conference, but the session topics for the conference were solicited over the course of a few months from the community through fliers and space science related newsletters.

Based on the session topics submitted and their related abstracts, the organizing committee arranged the sessions to accommodate the number of associated abstracts and compensated for topic similarity, merging or splitting sessions as needed. This approach successfully supported the wide range of software topics proposed without overwhelming the schedule or splitting into multiple tracks. Abstracts that were determined not to fit with the available session topics were combined into an "Open Oral" session on the last day.

Event Execution

The meeting was held from October 19 – 24, 2025 as a hybrid (in-person and online) event. The audio-visual was provided with a combination of WebEx sponsored by ESA, local expertise funded by the grant, and the hotel facilities. The DASH meeting was held from Monday to Wednesday at lunchtime with optional activities on the preceding Sunday and Wednesday afternoon. All presentations and posters are available in the [DASH 2025 Zenodo community](#).

Session leaders were free to select the format of their session and the technologies used during the session. Most used the standard presentation approach, with many allowing ample time for discussion whether immediately following each presentation or after a short sequence of presentations (e.g., panel discussions). Some selected additional technologies, such as Slido, Padlet, and Miro to increase anonymity of contributions and questions and encourage involvement from less extroverted participants. Presentations were required to be run from a main computer to reduce transition time between speakers. Designated DASH and IHDEA committee members were assigned to call on the virtual audience for questions to ensure space for their participation.

New for this year's DASH was a voluntary proposal writing workshop, which was held on Sunday, followed by a networking event. Also new for this year's meeting was the option for "Birds of a Feather" sessions, where interested attendees can gather without a planned agenda and discuss the stated topic, and a dedicated lightning talk session preceding a poster session. Poster presenters were asked to place their posters at the beginning of the meeting and leave them up until the end of DASH, allowing attendees to review the posters for the entirety of the meeting. The Appendix holds the full agenda.

A summary of the DASH agenda is as follows:

Monday's sessions

1. Keynote speaker: Dr. Stephen Fuselier on the Scientists / Data Interface.
2. Advancing Science Data Systems through Collaboration and Open-Source Solutions
3. Before Data: Software for Science Mission Planning and Operations
4. Novel Techniques and Infrastructure in Support of Heliophysics Modeling
5. Birds of a Feather: Open Source Software

Tuesday's sessions

1. Communities for Research Software Engineers
2. ML and LLM Applications in Heliophysics
3. Poster Lightning Talks
4. Poster Presentations
5. Birds of a Feather: Web Metrics for Data in the Era of AI.

Wednesday's sessions

1. Open Oral Session
2. Wrap Up

Once the workshop activities concluded, an optional boat ride through the famous Riverwalk of San Antonio was chartered for our attendees and their guests.

Scientific Program Highlights

Proposal Writing Workshop

Sessions 1 & 2 on Sunday Oct 19th, 2026

Approximately 15 people participated either in person or online in the 2-hour Proposal Writing Workshop on the Sunday preceding DASH. The workshop consisted of a 1-hour team presentation with an ice-breaker activity to outline the proposal process, necessary components, and sage advice for writing proposals for software. Geared towards software developers, the content was presented without presuming any previous experience or exposure to the proposal process. After a networking break, the participants spent the remaining hour working together to draft their own short proposals according to a template, a fake announcement of opportunity, and a rubric, and then assess the other group's proposals according to the same rubric. Based on the content of the proposals, the attendees had reasonably productive conversations and benefitted from the guidance given in the first half of the workshop. The materials are available on the DASH Zenodo community¹.

The winning proposal team with some of the organizers. L-R: Arnaud Masson, Jon Vandegriff, Arpiar Grigorian, Sanjay Kumar, Shirsh Lata Soni, Doug Rodgers, and Rebecca Ringuette.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17392275>

Keynote Speaker : Stephen Fuselier

DASH: Monday Session 1

Our keynote speaker kicked off DASH with a presentation on challenges for our field. Dr. Stephen Fuselier talked about the Scientist/Data Scientist interface, describing how the scientist and software developer/data scientist are still relevant in the age of AI. The presentation was followed by a short discussion on the topic.

Advancing Science Data Systems through Collaboration and Open-Source Solutions

DASH: Monday Session 2

Science data systems are vital for scientific discovery, yet their development has often been isolated within individual mission teams. Open-source software is reshaping this landscape by promoting collaboration and delivering reusable tools that enhance efficiency and impact. However, challenges remain, including a lack of feedback between open-source developers, mission teams, and the scientific research community.

Before Data: Software for Science Mission Planning and Operations

DASH: Monday Session 3

Modeling, simulation, and software architecture in the heliophysics community has tended to focus on modeling of physical phenomena to compare against observational data collected, or how to process and maximize scientific advances with that data. Long before that data has been collected, a science mission must be imagined, planned, refined, proposed, designed, built, launched, and operated... all by a mélange of software that is guided by—but never touches—the science data.

Novel Techniques and Infrastructure in Support of Heliophysics Modeling

DASH: Monday Session 4

Heliophysics models and coupled modeling frameworks play an important role in advancing our understanding of the Sun and its impact on the human environment and activities. Modern models are an intricate amalgamation of complex software systems, convoluted data pipelines, and multi-stage analysis frameworks, requiring a diverse set of science and technology skills. The goal of this session was to share experience on the novel and cutting-edge technological ideas and solutions pertaining to the field of heliophysical models, as well as supporting software and infrastructure.

BOF #1: Open Source Software

DASH: Monday Session 5

The discussion touched on many topics, including specific tooling and advice for open source software, how to convince institutes to create open source code, whether releasing open source code cost a competitive advantage or not, collaboration and creating effective open source libraries, whether it is worth open-sourcing tools if there isn't a high demand, and the observed shift of the "industry" towards Python. This last topic highlighting the current prevalence of Python had particularly lively discussion with attendees pointing out the permanent need for C, C++, and FORTRAN as languages "closer to the machine" for more advanced computational demands.

Communities for Research Software Engineers

DASH: Tuesday Session 1

The session featured Miranda Mundt of the U.S. Research Software Engineer organization (<https://us-rse.org/>) speaking on "Technical communities of practice: Benefits of participating, lessons learned from managing, and how to foster belonging" and Jonathan Niehof speaking from a Heliophysics research software engineer (RSE) perspective. One of the ten key takeaways from the 2024 Software for the NASA SMD Workshop Report (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14047904>), communities of practice for software presents a timely but poorly understood topic in the Heliophysics software development community. Peer mentoring in software, or "pair programming", was promoted by both participants as highly beneficial for the RSEs involved and a proven way to increase the production efficiency and quality of the generated software. At least half the audience or more were also interested in affinity groups that meet virtually every quarter with an in-person component at the yearly conference and a newsletter for RSEs in Heliophysics. The newsletter content considered to be useful included summaries of the previous meeting, previews of the next one, opportunities, short descriptions of what changed on the group's website (implying that there should be one), and lists of deadlines for relevant upcoming conferences.

ML and LLM Applications in Heliophysics

DASH: Tuesday Session 2

Machine Learning (ML) techniques and Large Language Models (LLMs) are transforming research and data analysis in the Heliophysics community. Talks highlighted ML-driven approaches to challenges such as solar wind classification, radio imaging spectroscopy, and real-time event detection, as well as practical LLM applications including generating code from natural language queries, extracting information from scientific literature, and working agentially with codebases.

Posters and Lightning Talks

DASH: Tuesday Sessions 3 & 4

All poster presenters were encouraged to give a one minute “lightning talk” to generate interest in their posters. These talks were then followed by a poster session accompanied by drinks and snacks to encourage networking, discussion, and collaboration.

BOF #2: Web Metrics in the Era of Artificial Intelligence

DASH: Tuesday Session 5

A BOF on web metrics for data archives highlighted significant challenges posed by AI-driven bots and crawlers, including what was perceived as corrupt usage statistics and performance degradation. The session fostered productive discussion on mitigation strategies, such as IP intelligence tools, rate limiting, machine-learning-based detection, and access controls, while raising important questions about preserving open-access principles.

DASH Open Oral Session

DASH: Wednesday Session 1

Presentations emphasized improving interoperability, accessibility, and usability of heliophysics data and software. Key themes included Open Science mandates driving the release of previously private modeling codes, innovative software pipelines significantly improving data quality and accessibility, and the growing importance of metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and streamline workflows. Discussions identified future challenges and opportunities, such as the need for standardized metadata for adaptive-grid HDF5 and NetCDF4 data, and new approaches for presenting large, complex datasets to users in a cost-effective way.

Wrap-Up / Feedback

DASH: Wednesday Session 2

The final session of DASH started with an announcement of the location of the next DASH and IHDEA meetings - Dublin, Ireland for 2026. Those interested were also invited to propose to host the 2027 DASH meeting. This final session also was an open forum for discussion about the meeting and provided the attendees the opportunity to provide immediate feedback on the DASH portion of the workshop. See the conclusion section of this report for a summary of the participant feedback.

IHDEA General Forum and Governance

The IHDEA (International Heliophysics Data Environment Alliance, <https://ihdea.net>) met on the last two days of the week. The IHDEA meeting focused on updates from the Heliophysics data community, report outs from current working groups, and discussions of relevant drivers and current standards, including their governance. All presentations are available online in the [IHDEA 2025 Zenodo community](#).

Thursday: Space Agencies and Institutions Reports

The first day of the IHDEA portion of the meeting started with a report out of space agency and institution activities. Members organizations (and their presenters) represented at the meeting included:

- JAXA (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency) and Nagoya University (Yoshi Miyoshi),
- Plasma Physics Data Center (CDPP)/CNES (Daniele Boucon),
- Korea Astronomy and Space Science Institute (KASI) (Ji-Hye Baek),
- Observatoire de Paris (Baptiste Cecconi),
- NASA's Community Coordinated Modeling Center (CCMC) (Darren De Zeeuw),
- European Space Agency (ESA) (Arnaud Masson),
- NASA's Heliophysics Digital Resource Library (HDRL) (Rebecca Ringuette),
- The Virtual Solar Observatory (VSO) (Edward Mansky),
- NASA's Space Physics Data Facility (SPDF) (Eric Grimes)

Common themes in these reports included details on the development of new capabilities, notes about the nature and value of collaborations with other institutions, and the use of SPASE metadata, where SPASE is the Space Physics Archive Search Extract (SPASE²) metadata model currently used to describe multiple types of resources in the international Heliophysics data environment.

Thursday: Working Group Reports 1 and 2

Two sessions were then held to allow for the IHDEA working groups to report out. The following working groups reported:

Science Platforms Coordination (Shawn Polson and Jan Reerink)

The Science Platforms Coordination presented a small selection of software analysis environments crafted based on community-guided selection of software, which were successfully demonstrated as interoperable with multiple cloud platforms including HelioCloud and ESA's DataLabs.

² <https://spase-group.org/>

SPASE Information Model

(Arnaud Masson)

The SPASE Information Model presentation updated attendees on a short list of model improvements and changes in the past year, along with the recent leadership change in that group. In an invited talk presented by Joana Oliveira, the SPASE metadata registry for ESA Heliophysics missions showed ESA's progress on creating DOIs for missions and their instruments.

Python Adoption

(Julie Barnum)

The Python Adoption group leader discussed progress towards community adoption of Python software standards for Heliophysics, including a tiering system prioritizing open science characteristics such as reusability, interoperability, and discoverability.

DOIs for Science

(Rebecca Ringuette)

A short presentation on the large variety of persistent identifiers (PIDs) available for use in Heliophysics metadata provided motivation to shift from a currently narrow focus on DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) as the primary identifier for Heliophysics towards the larger PID landscape.

Semantics (Provisional)

(Ryan McGanaghan and Baptiste Cecconi)

This presentation made a call for coordinated community action in semantics to collect, curate, create and recognize important standards. HeliKNOW and a "knowledge commons" approach were presented as a means of achieving these goals and community members were solicited to participate

Data Access (Call to Action)

(Robert Weigel)

This presentation raised practical issues related to current implementations of metadata and data access, mostly between SPASE and HAPI (Heliophysics Application Programmer's Interface). The HAPI specification is focused on access and has stayed away from larger metadata issues but has encountered multiple areas where better standards or better implementations of current standards would be useful. Versioning for ISTP (International Solar Terrestrial Physics program) was called for, and better maintenance of metadata, especially if regular URLs are present instead of DOIs. Many of the issues could be addressed in the context of a more complete and active set of IHDEA working groups.

Thursday: SPASE 3.0 Report and Discussion

The last session of the first day was reserved for a presentation and question and answer session about the development of a next generation SPASE metadata model (“SPASE 3.0”). This session was led by Andriy Koval and overviewed the main use cases and progress to date on the model development. This session also featured time for discussion and questions from the community. The presentation was received favorably by the community with more detailed side discussions also producing agreement on the design decisions made so far.

Friday: Space Weather Standards: Compatibility between Research and Operations

The first session for this day was a special topic on “Space Weather Standards: compatibility between research and operations” led by Edmund Henley which drew a great deal of interest from the community. This session featured several talks by different speakers including an opening talk by Edmund Henley on “Better Together? An overview of terrestrial weather standards” followed by Bob Weigel with two talks : “A Recommendation for Units in Heliophysics Metadata” and “Preliminary Recommendations Related to Reference Frames (Coordinate Systems)”. The last talk in the session was by Mark Miesch who spoke about “Heliophysics Data Assimilation with JEDI: Standardization and Collaboration Enabled by a Community Model”. Overall, attendees showed interest in learning more about existing standards and interoperability achievements from the Earth sciences and other fields related to Heliophysics, and they appreciated the progress on units and reference frames standardization for Heliophysics.

Friday: General Forum

After a short break a general forum of the IHDEA community was held to consider changes in governance for IHDEA. The community present both in the room and online were polled for their approval of the proposals of bylaw and charter changes. The community successfully approved three of these changes which were aimed at improving governance, flexibility, and community engagement which included:

1. **Working Groups:** Replacing subcommittees with time-limited, community-driven working groups.
2. **Balanced Representation:** Limiting voting representatives to two per major agency or stakeholder.
3. **More Agile Decision-Making:** Allowing simple majority decisions for executive actions which previously required unanimous consent.

All changes were approved by more than two-thirds of members present reflecting strong consensus and support.

Friday: Decadal Community Response

After lunch the Decadal Community Response session was a purposefully interactive session, involving the use of Miro boards and small and large group discussions³. The three concepts that rose to the top were:

1. A new **longer-term funding structure** designed to enhance collaboration, reuse, and maintenance of software;
2. The purposeful development of **interoperable mission tools** through cross-institutional development; and
3. **Increased collaboration with efforts in other sciences** through involvement in their conferences covering standards and archiving efforts.

The first topic is one that has been highly prioritized by the software community in other workshop reports in recent years (e.g., Ringuette et al. 2024⁴ and Ringuette et al. 2025⁵). However, the topic was skipped due to the then ongoing U.S. government shutdown and the resulting funders not able to attend the meeting.

Topic 2 drew the most discussion. There was general agreement that a slightly higher level of funding will be needed due to challenges of collaborating across institutions and the extra work to increase reusability of mission software. However, there was also palpable optimism that this slight increase of funding would more than pay off once a few foundational software packages were created from currently existing options. Then, the community could shift to contributing to existing tools to increase applicability to new missions or provide high quality justifications why a new tool would be needed.

Topic 3 can be succinctly summarized by a paraphrase of a participant's comment, 'Look at what others are doing!' There was strong interest to collaborate with related fields (e.g., by attending the ESIP⁶ and RDA⁷ workshops) and across data repositories to develop and shift standards in Heliophysics to take advantage of where standards in other fields have demonstrated benefit. This could be through a yearly workshop focused on data repositories and services where the international Heliophysics data archiving community shares their challenges and recently solved problems.

Friday: Wrap Up

A final plenary session concluded the meeting with gratitudes and accolades to the local organizers and the participants for a successful meeting.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19139264>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14047903>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17613135>

⁶ Earth Science Information Partners, <https://www.esipfed.org/>

⁷ Research Data Alliance, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

Conclusion

The 2025 DASH/IHDEA meetings demonstrated that a thriving, engaged, and forward-looking community in heliophysics data, software and analytics exists. Strong attendance with a notable number of early career participants, effective hybrid delivery, and productive discussions across software, technology, and governance all contributed to making these meetings highly successful. This level of interest and engagement by the participants provide evidence that these meetings are valuable and are a strong foundation for the 2026 meetings and beyond.

Feedback

A summary of the feedback received appears below, grouped into a few general themes as follows.

Attendance and Community Engagement

This year's meeting had similar attendance compared to previous DASH meetings, despite broader logistical and funding challenges for the U.S.-based participants that year. Early-career researchers and young professionals demonstrated strong engagement in the sessions, contributing to an energetic and forward-looking atmosphere. There was also consistent engagement across the various sessions, posters, BOFs, and discussions.

Hybrid and Virtual Participation

Virtual participants consistently praised the high-quality audio throughout the meeting and the active monitoring of online reactions and questions. A key recommendation from the feedback is to continue assigning a dedicated on-site committee member to monitor the virtual chat, rather than rotating this responsibility among session chairs. This approach provides consistency, continuity, and a clear point of contact for remote attendees.

Technology and Tools

The continued use of **Zenodo communities** for archiving all talks and posters presented at the meeting was strongly supported. Modern tools such as **Slido** were particularly effective for surfacing popular questions during panel discussions, enhancing interactivity for both virtual and in-person participants. Participant feedback on using collaborative tools (e.g., Miro boards) was mixed, with some negative feedback on the large variety of tools used by the different sessions.

This feedback suggests a balanced approach: embrace useful modern technologies, but avoid introducing **too many new tools at once**, to reduce cognitive and logistical overhead. One way to do this is to predetermine a small set of tools recommended for use in sessions for various capabilities to avoid an onslaught of tools for attendees to

learn (e.g., padlet for brainstorming ideas or posting questions rather than padlet, slido, mentimeter, etc.).

Birds-of-a-Feather (BOF) Sessions

The two BOF sessions during DASH were well attended and generated active discussion. The feedback on these sessions was very positive, with some participants suggesting that BOFs could be more tightly integrated into the daily schedule, specifically for there to be no long break between the main program and BOFs. Some suggested that to encourage attendance and discussion at the BOFs refreshments or drinks could be made available.

Posters and Lightning Talks

The dedicated poster session was highly appreciated. Participants valued having posters displayed for the entire duration of the meeting, increasing visibility and informal discussion opportunities. The preceding lightning talks effectively complemented the poster session and helped attendees identify posters of interest.

Areas for Improvement and Future Directions

Based on the feedback obtained during the meeting and through the post-workshop survey, several areas of improvement were identified.

Supporting the Next Generation

Greater involvement of early-career researchers and research software engineers (RSEs) was commonly mentioned as a priority for future DASH/IHDEA meetings. One proposed method to accomplish this was a dedicated early-career BOF to allow junior participants to discuss challenges and opportunities among themselves. As discussed in the *Communities for Research Software Engineers* session, there was also overall interest in adding more of a community component to DASH similar to what is available through the US-RSE and similar organizations. An action for the DASH community is to determine what components we might add to future meetings which better support early career RSEs, such as those discussed in the RSE subsection above and increasing communication with leaders of the RSE meetings for sharing lessons learned.

Broadening Community Involvement

It was noted that several significant communities were not well represented at the meeting. The number of attendees from the **numerical simulation and modeling** software engineers and the **ground-based observation** data communities were notably low, demonstrating a need for increased involvement with those communities. A follow-up action should be to discuss with the members of these communities who did attend DASH/IHDEA and ask what we could do to make the meetings more attractive.

Networking and Career Development

Feedback also pointed to interest in structured networking opportunities for attendees seeking employment, such as a small “job fair”. Potential formats include job-focused networking sessions held during or immediately after the poster session, possibly in dedicated rooms. Companies and organizations associated with the RSE community could be invited to recruit new employees at DASH/IHDEA. Making space in the meeting to host tables or areas where members can engage with these employers should be considered.

Planning Ahead

Feedback indicated that early October should be avoided due to the increased risk of U.S. government shutdowns for future meetings. The U.S. RSE community has expressed interest in a joint meeting in 2027, which could be achieved in a variety of ways, such as

- An RSE-focused session at the DASH meeting,
- Inviting UK and Ireland RSE and/or RSE-adjacent communities (such as EHC⁸), acknowledging the origins of the RSE concept in the UK, and
- An overlapping day or jointly organized session to foster cross-community collaboration.

Next Steps

This year, the DASH and IHDEA meeting had strong attendance despite broader logistical and funding challenges for the U.S.-based participants that year. Strong participation from early-career researchers and young professionals contributed to an energetic and forward-looking atmosphere. The 2026 meeting will be held in Dublin Ireland in October 2026. We look forward to working with the local organizing committee to incorporate this feedback and continue to improve the experience and value of these meetings for the community. This document identifies many actions we can take to improve the meetings which broadly include considering new content for the agenda, following up with underrepresented and early career community members to understand how to improve its attractiveness and value, limiting the number of technologies which support the meeting, and of course keeping highly appreciated content such as lightning talks and a dedicated poster session.

⁸ [EGUsphere - Establishing a European Heliophysics Community \(EHC\)](#)

Appendix - Meeting Agenda

Day 0 (Sunday)	Start	Stop
Registration	13:00	14:00
Proposal Writing Workshop Part 1	14:00	15:00
Break	15:00	15:30
Proposal Writing Workshop Part 2	15:30	16:30
Evening Social Meet and Greet	16:30	18:30
DASH Day 1 (Monday)	Start	Stop
Registration & Coffee	8:00	9:00
Opening Welcome!	9:00	9:10
Invited Speaker + Q&A (Decadal)	9:10	10:00
Break / Networking	10:00	10:30
Advancing Science Data Systems through Collaboration and Open-Source Solutions	10:30	12:00
Lunch	12:00	13:30
Before Data: Software for Science Mission Planning and Operations (But Not Data Pipelines)	13:30	15:00
Break / Networking	15:00	15:30
Novel techniques and infrastructure in support of Heliophysics modelling	15:30	17:00
Announcements	17:00	17:10
Dinner	17:10	18:40
BOF Sessions	18:40	19:40
DASH Day 2 (Tuesday)		
Opening Welcome!	9:00	9:10
RSE Speakers + Q&A	9:10	10:00
Break / Networking	10:00	10:30
LLM Application in Heliophysics	10:30	12:00
Lunch	12:00	13:30
Lightning Talks	13:30	14:30
Group Photo / Break	14:30	15:00
Poster Session / Drinks	15:00	17:00
Announcements	17:00	17:10

Dinner	17:10	18:40
BOF Sessions	18:40	19:40
DASH Day 3 (Wednesday)	Start	Stop
Registration & Coffee	8:00	9:00
Opening Welcome!	9:00	9:10
Open Oral Session	9:10	10:40
Break / Networking	10:40	11:10
Wrap Up	11:10	12:40
Lunch on your Own	12:40	14:00
Boat Ride	14:00	15:30
IHDEA Day 1 (Thursday)	Start	Stop
Opening Welcome!	9:00	9:10
Space Agencies and Institutions Reports	9:10	11:10
Break / Networking	11:10	11:40
IHDEA Working Group Reports 1	11:40	12:40
Lunch	12:40	14:10
IHDEA Working Group Reports 2	14:10	15:10
Break / Networking	15:10	15:40
SPASE 3.0 Report and Discussion	15:40	17:10
Announcements	17:10	17:20
IHDEA Day 2 (Friday)	Start	Stop
Opening Welcome!	9:00	9:10
Special Session 1: Space Weather Standards	9:10	10:40
Break / Networking	10:40	11:10
IHDEA General Forum	11:10	12:40
Lunch	12:40	13:40
Special Session 2: Decadal Community Response	13:40	14:40
Break / Networking	14:40	14:55
Open Presentations Session	14:55	15:25
Final Words / Wrap up	15:25	15:55